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A REVIEW ON IMMUNITY BOOSTER- A HERBAL REMEDY TO FIGHT AGAINST COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

This review focused on the use of plant-based foods and herbal pharmaceutical formulation for enhancing the immunity against COVID-19. In humans, corona viruses are causing the common cold and, recently, severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) these present a major threat to public health. The novel corona virus has spread rapidly to multiple countries and has been declared a pandemic by the WHO. COVID-19 is usually caused a virus to which most probably the people with low immunity response are being affected. Plant-based foods increased the intestinal beneficial bacteria which are helpful and make up the immune system. By the use of plenty of water, minerals like magnesium and Zinc, micronutrients, herbs, food rich in vitamins C, D and E, and better life style one can promote the health and can overcome this infection. Various studies investigated that a powerful antioxidant glutathione and a bioflavonoid quercetin may prevent various infections including COVID-19. In conclusion, the plant-based foods play a vital role to enhance the immunity of people to control of COVID-19.

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INTRODUCTION

To fight against different dangerous infections it is must to have strong immune system. Immunity cannot built in a day or a week, but taking a well-balanced diet to keep our body in a good physical and mental health builds our immune system automatically stronger^[1]. Immune system is a network of special cells, tissues, proteins and organs^[1, 2]. Immunity is the state of protection against infectious disease conferred either through an immune response generated by immunization or previous infection or by other non-immunological factors. This article reviews on active and passive immunity and the differences between them: it also describes the various immunity booster and mechanism of immune system in human body^[1, 3]

With the 2019 corona virus COVID-19 pandemic, it's especially important to and proper hygiene practices can protect any person from COVID-19. Currently, no research supports the use of any food supplement to protect against COVID-19 specifically. Our immune system consists of a complex collection of cells, processes, and chemicals that constantly defends body against invading pathogens, including viruses, toxins, and bacteria.^[1, 2] 'Keeping our immune system healthy year-round is key to preventing infection and disease. Making healthy lifestyle choices by consuming nutritious foods and getting enough sleep and exercise are the most important ways to boost our immune system. In addition, research has shown that supplementing with certain vitamins, minerals, herbs, and other substances can improve immune response and potentially protect against illness.^[2, 3]

The COVID-19 virus' morphological characteristics and chemical composition are similar to other human surrogate corona viruses on which data are available to both sustainability in the environment and efficient coagulation measures.^[2, 3] Although drinking water does not ensure that you would not contract the corona virus, remaining hydrated can improve your health and make sure the immune system can defeat the virus if it is transferred to you. The drinking water works to help your cells to oxygenate. Cells can compete at their best if they get enough oxygen that helps them protect the body from any infectious agents. Main objective of this review is to provide information about all type impurity boosters available in nature and market

Types of immunity

Immune system can be divided into two parts-innate and adaptive. Our first line of defense- the natural protection power we are born with is innate immunity and this innate response act quickly. The protection that we gain through life when we are exposed to various diseases or protection against them for vaccination is adaptive immunity, this adaptive immunity generates antibodies went it spots an enemy in the body. The adaptive immunity takes 5-10 days to generate antibodies and meanwhile innate immunity keeps fighting to maintain the levels of pathogens at a bay.^[4, 6, 8]

INNATE IMMUNE RESPONSE

In an infectious process, the most common host response is to generate inflammation. Viruses in the absence of cytopathologic damage at early stages of infection inhibit the induction of acute phase protein response because early monocytes are not activated.^[4, 5] By contrast, the participation of NK cells against the virus play an important role in the host's defense, they recognize cells infected by viruses in an antigen-independent manner, exert cytotoxic activities and rapidly produce large amounts of IFN- γ that participate in the activation of the adaptive immune cell.^[4] Type I interferons are the major cytokines responsible for defending the human host against viral infections. It has been shown that interferons do not exert their antiviral effects by direct action on viruses, but they help in the gene activation that results in the production of antiviral proteins, which participate as mediators in the inhibition of viral replication, as well as mediating the effects of suppressor T cells. The adaptive immune response against this type of infection is primarily composed of the humoral immune response with the antibody production directed against viral antigens. However, the cellular immune response is the most important for virus eradication.^[6]

T CD4+ cells recognize antigens presented by MHC-II molecules on the surface of APCs. Subsequently, T CD4+ cells perform multiple effector functions including direct activation of antigen-specific macrophages and B cells, as well as cytokine-dependent activation of T CD8+ cells. T CD8+ cells eliminate virus-infected cells and secrete cytokines such as TNF- α and IFN- γ , which also participate in the inhibition of viral replication.^[5, 6] Thus, both the innate immune response and the adaptive immune response in their cellular and humoral involvement eradicate viral infections in most cases,. However, certain viruses have developed mechanisms of immune evasion to survive longer and thus be able to replicate without any problem until causing serious damage to the host.^[6, 16]

ACQUIRED IMMUNE RESPONSE

Acquired immunity relies on the capacity of immune cells to distinguish between the body's own cells and unwanted invaders. The host's cells express "self" antigens. These antigens are different from those on the surface of bacteria or on the surface of virus-infected host cells ("non-self" or "foreign" antigens). Micro-organisms that overcome or circumvent the innate non-specific defence mechanisms or are administered deliberately (i.e. active immunization) come up against the host's second line of defense: acquired immunity.^[6] The cells that respond are recommitted, because of their surface receptors, to respond to a particular epitope on the antigen. This response takes two forms, humoral and cell mediated, which usually develop in parallel. The part played by each depends on a number of factors, including the nature of the antigen, the route of entry and the individual who is infected. Humeral immunity depends on the appearance in the blood of antibodies produced by plasma cells.^[5, 6] the term 'cell-mediated immunity' was originally coined to describe localized reactions to organisms mediated by T lymphocytes and phagocytes rather than by antibody. It is now used to describe any response in which antibody plays a subordinate role. Cell-mediated immunity depends mainly on the development of T cells that are specifically responsive to the inducing agent, and is generally active against intracellular organisms Specific immunity may be acquired in two main ways:

1. Induced by overt clinical infection or inapparent clinical infection
2. Deliberate artificial immunization. This is active acquired immunity, and contrasts with passive acquired immunity, This is the transfer of preformed antibodies to a non-immune individual by means of blood, serum components or lymphoid cells.

Mechanisms

The immune mechanism can be produced when the infection agents attack our body or going through vaccination.^[7] However, the same immune mechanism (antibodies and cytotoxic T cells) which were discussed earlier, in certain situations can cause the destruction to the cells or tissues in our body.^[8,9]

Microphage captures, engulfs and digests an antigen. Microphage presents a fragment of the antigen on its surface and then interaction between proteins on the microphage and helper T cell occurs, activating the helper T cell. The helper T cell proliferates into either TH 1 or TH 2 cells, which secrete different types of cytokines. Cytokines secreted by the TH 1 cell activate cytotoxic T cells to kill the infected target cell.^[9, 10]

Fig 1- Mechanism of immunity booster.

Immunity Boosters:

A healthy immune system protects us by first creating a barrier that stops those invaders, or antigens, from entering the body.^[8] And if one slips by the barrier, the immune system produces white blood cells, and other chemicals and proteins that attack and destroy these foreign substances.^[11] To boost immunity means intake or consumption of certain food that provides additional benefits to the body. To boost immunity it's important to take the right kind of foods in the right quantities.^[9]

Fig 2- Types of Immunity booster.

Food:

There is some evidence that various micronutrient deficiencies^[12]

For example, deficiencies of zinc, iron, and vitamins A, B6, C, and E — alter immune responses

Zinc containing

Zinc is a mineral that's commonly added to supplements and other healthcare products like lozenges that are meant to boost your immune system.^[12, 13] Zinc is needed for immune cell development and communication and plays an important role in inflammatory response

Iron containing

Iron plays an important role in immune function. A diet containing too little iron can cause anemia and weaken the immune system. Foods rich in iron include meat, poultry, fish, shellfish, legumes, nuts, seeds, cruciferous vegetables and dried fruit.^[12] Combining iron-rich foods with vitamin C can help boost your absorption even further. Keep in mind, however, that overly high iron levels in your blood can be harmful and may actually suppress the immune system. Therefore, it's best to take iron supplements only if you have an iron deficiency.^[13]

Vitamins containing

Vitamin C

Vitamin C increases blood levels of antibodies and helps to differentiate lymphocyte (white blood cells), which helps the body, determine what kind of protection is needed. One can easily consume 200 mg of vitamin C from a combination of foods such as oranges, grapefruit, kiwi, strawberries, Brussels sprouts, red and green peppers, broccoli, cooked cabbage and cauliflower. Vitamin C also functions as a powerful antioxidant, protecting against damage induced by oxidative stress, which occurs with the accumulation of reactive molecules known as free radicals.^{[12] [13]}

Vitamin E

Vitamin E is vital for maintaining the overall health of elderly people, including their immunity. Vitamin E is a powerful antioxidant that can protect you from various infections, bacteria, and viruses. Soaked almonds, peanut butter, sunflower seeds, and even hazelnuts should be consumed to get the daily dose of vitamin E.^[12]

Vitamin A

Beta carotene gets converted to vitamin A, which is essential for a strong immune system. It works by helping antibodies respond to toxins and foreign substances. Good sources of beta carotene include sweet potatoes, carrots, mangoes, apricots, spinach, kale, broccoli, squash and cantaloupe. It Promoting growth and development, and protecting epithelium and mucus integrity in the body. ^[12, 14]

Vitamin B complex

B vitamins, including B12 and B6, are important for healthy immune response. Yet, significantly affects your immune system's ability to function properly, resulting in an increased risk of infection and disease ^[14]

MEDICINAL SUPPLEMENTS**Herbal**

According to WHO around 80% of world's population uses herbal medicines to boost their immunity. And maintain a primary health. According to research has found that various herbs that possess immune-stimulating properties as a useful feature. ^[13]

Ashwagandha

On oral administration, Ashwagandha churn showed a significant increase in neutrophil adhesion and delayed-type hypersensitivity (DTH) response. It is concluded that Ashwagandha churn significantly potentiated the cellular immunity ^[14]

Synonym: Withania somnifera

Family: Solanaceae

Species: W. Somnifera

Biological name: Withania somnifera

Biological role: antioxidant

Ashwagandha also provides numerous other benefits for your body and brain. For example, it can boost brain function, lower blood sugar and cortisol levels, and help fight symptoms of anxiety and depression.

Use: A team of Portland medical researchers has found that drinking whole cows' milk with Ashwagandha; an herb used for more than 5,000 years in the practice of Ayurvedic medicine can increase the body's white blood cells, which help boost immunity. ^[21]

Gulvel

It has been reported that Gulvel have potential immunomodulatory and cytotoxic effect. They have been reported to function by boosting phagocytosis activity of microphages, production ROS in human neutrophil cell, enhancement in nitric oxide production by stimulation of microphages. ^[12, 14]

Synonym: Tinospora cordifolia

Family: Menispermaceae

Species: T. Cordifolia

Chemical constituents: Active compounds 11-hydroxymustakone, N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone, N-formylannonain, cordifolioside A, magnoflorine, tinocordiside and syringin

Biological name: Tinospora cordifolia

Biological role: Tinospora cordifolia extracts are extensively used in various herbal preparations for the treatment of different ailments for its anti-periodic, anti-spasmodic, anti-microbial, anti-osteoporotic, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis, anti-allergic, and anti-diabetic properties

Use: Tinospora cordifolia has an importance in traditional Ayurvedic medicine used for ages in the treatment of fever, jaundice, chronic diarrhea, cancer, dysentery, bone fracture, pain, asthma, skin disease, poisonous insect, snake bite, eye disorders. ^[12,14,15]

Amala

The fruit extract of *Emblica officinalis* (Alma) has been shown to have free radical scavenging activity and immunomodulatory properties

Synonyms: cicca emblica, diesperus emblica

Family: Phyllanthaceae

Species: P.emblica

Botanical name: Phyllanthus emblica Emblica arborea Raf, Amla.

Chemical constituents: emblicanin A (37%), emblicanin B (33%), punigluconin (12%), and pedunculagin (14%).^[10] Amla also contains punicafolin and phyllanemblinin A, phyllanemblin other polyphenols, such as flavonoids, kaempferol, ellagic acid, and gallic acid.

Uses:-

- Amla is vitamin c rich fruit which boost the production of white blood cell (WBC) in the body that help in fighting several infections and diseases.
- Amla is also rich in Iron, calcium and several other mineral which make the complete nutritional fruit. ^[12, 18]

Tulsi

Tulsi is extremely useful for treating bacterial and fungal infections as well as immunological disorders like allergies and asthma. Explaining the benefits of Tulsi, Haritha says, "It is rich in Vitamin C and Zinc and acts as a natural immune booster"^[12, 14]

Synonym: Ocimum sanctum

Family: Lamiaceae

Species: o.tenuiflorum

Biological name: Ocimum tenuiflorum

Biological role:

- 1) Antibiotic
- 2) Antiviral
- 3) Anti-stress agent
- 4) anti- inflamentry
- 5) Anti-fungal
- 6) Anti-bacterial

Chemical constituents: Oleanolic acid, Ursolic acid, Rosmarinic acid, Eugenol, Carvacrol, Linalool, and β -caryophyllene.

Uses: Tulsi plant indoors can help protect you from certain infections and diseases such as cold, cough, and viral infections. These strong disinfectant and germicidal factors are not the only reason why Tulsi is a great herb for boosting your immunity.^[16]

Neem

Purified extracts of Neem contained immunomodulators that stimulate the cells and macrophages that terminate

Synonym: Azadirachta indica.

Family: Meliaceae

Species: A. indica

Chemical constituents:

A) Neem leaves: Azadirachtin, meliacin, quercitin, nembosterol, ascorbic acid, carotenoids, amino acid etc.

B) Neem seed: Azadirachtin

C) Neem kernals : oil of margosa.

D) Neem barks: Nimbin, nimbinine, nimbidine, nimbosterol , nimbidol and margosin.

Biological source: Neem consists of the fresh or dried leaves and seed oil of Azadirachta indica

Biological role: Neem (Azadirachta indica) plants parts shows antimicrobial role through inhibitory effect on microbial growth/potentiality of cell wall breakdown. Azadirachtin, a complex tetranortriterpenoid limonoid present in seeds, is the key constituent responsible for both antifeedant and toxic effects in insects

Use: Neem helps boost your immune system while cooling down your body internally. It possesses both anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties that help keep your skin clean, radiant and healthy. Neem also has blood-purifying properties.^[12, 14, 16, 22]

Garlic

Garlic is considered as a capable candidate for maintaining the homeostasis of the immune system. It has been found that garlic protein fraction has a stimulatory effect on lymphocyte, Natural Killer (NK) cells, and macrophages cytotoxicity

Synonym: Allium sativum, chive

Family: liliaceae

Species: A.Sativim

Chemical constituents: carbohydrates, protein, mucilago.etc

Biological source: It consists of ripe bulbs of allium sativum.

Biological role: 1) antioxidant

2) anti-inflamentry

3) Immunomodulator

4) Antibacterial

5) Antifungal

Uses: The main ingredient of garlic which fights the germs is Allicin and the best way to use garlic as an immune booster is to eat it raw. Chewing garlic releases the Allicin in the mouth which is then absorbed by the body.^[14, 17]

Turmeric

Synonyms: Curcuma domenstica valenton

Family: Zingiberaceae

Species: C.longa

Bionamial name: Curcuma longa

Biological role: 1) Antiseptic

2) Immunomodulater

3) Anti-inflamentry

Chemical constituents: Turmeric powder is about 60–70% carbohydrates, 6–13% water, 6–8% protein, 5–10% fat, 3–7% dietary minerals, 3–7% essential oils, 2–7% dietary fiber, and 1–6% curcuminoids.

Uses

Turmeric is among the richest food source of Iron 67.8mg per 100g of turmeric powder.

One teaspoon (3g) of turmeric powder provides 2mg of Iron. Iron is important for improve immunities power and turmeric have riches Iron.^[14,15]

Aloevera**Synonym:** Aloe barbadensis Mill, Aloe indica royal.**Family:** Asphodelaceae**Species:** A.vera **Binomial name:** Aloe vera**Chemical constituents:** vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids and amino acids. Vitamins: It contains vitamins A (beta-carotene), C and E, which are antioxidants. It also contains vitamin B12, folic acid, and choline.**Uses:**

- Support the immune and cardiovascular system
- Aloe Vera contain amino acid, minerals, vitamins ^[14, 16]

Ginger

Ginger is one of the most effective natural Immunomodulator. In vitro study found that ginger inhibited lymphocyte proliferation; this was mediated by reductions in IL-2 and IL-10 production [26]. Ginger essential oil showed improvement in humoral and cell mediated immune response in immune suppressed mice.

Synonym: zinziber, beans, bounce**Family:** Zingiberaceae**Species:** Z. officinale**Chemical constituents:** 6 - gingerol, 6 - shogal, 6 - parasol**Biological source:** Ginger consists of the rhizomes, Roscoe and dried in the sun.

- Biological role:**
- 1) Antioxidant
 - 2) Anti- inflamentry
 - 3) Anticancer
 - 4) Immunomodulatory
 - 5) Antidiabetic.

Use: ginger can help improve immune health due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. In fact, starting your morning with a glass of ginger tea or ginger kashayam may ward off illness and boost the immune system. ^[18, 14]

Allopathic**Multivitamin Tablet**

Multivitamins are used to provide vitamins that are not taken in through the diet. Essential roles of vitamins in modulating a broad range of immune processes, such as lymphocyte activation and proliferation, T-helper-cell differentiation, tissue-specific lymphocyte homing, the production of specific antibody isotopes and regulation of the immune response.

Antioxidants Tablet

Glutathione is a powerful antioxidant in the body, it scavenges damaging free radicals and is involved in tissue repair and builds chemicals and proteins that are used for the immune system. N-Acetylcysteine, or NAC, promotes the production of glutathione and is also used as a supplement. Studies in animal models of other viral infections have shown that NAC reduced the severity and duration of symptoms by increasing cellular defense and repair (A). NAC is taken in doses of 500-600 mg. Glutathione can be taken orally 500 mg or by IV 400–2400 mg with a doctor's order. Quercetin is a bioflavonoid found in a variety of fruits and vegetables. Animal and laboratory studies have demonstrated that quercetin can inhibit a wide range of virus infections including a COVID-19-related corona virus SARS CoV. Quercetin support antioxidant capacity and protects lung tissue. As a supplement is combined with vitamin C, bromelain is sold as a single supplement. Recommendation is between 500 and 1000 mg daily. Major sources are leafy green vegetables, dill, peppers, apples, grapes, fennel leaf, red onion, oregano, chili pepper, green tea, and black tea. ^[19,20]

Other ways to boost the immune system

Life Styles

- Avoiding smoking.
- Exercising regularly.
- Maintaining a healthy weight.
- Avoiding alcohol or drinking in moderation.
- Getting enough sleep.
- Minimizing stress.
- Practicing correct hand-washing and oral hygiene.

Exercise-

Maintaining a healthy and balanced diet, exercising regularly, and getting enough sleep can help keep your body and your immune system working well.

Manage stress-

Research has shown that high stress levels may impair the immune system. So whenever possible, try to be aware of your stress levels and work to lower them when they get too high.

Sleep-

First, we will give a short overview of the signals which mediate the communication between the nervous and immune system and thus provide the basis for the influence of sleep on immune processes. Because normally sleep is embedded in the circadian sleep–wake rhythm, we will then review studies that examined immune changes associated with the sleep (or rest) phase of this rhythm, without attempting to isolate the effects of sleep per se from those of circadian rhythm. ^[14,20]

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Conflict of interest

Nil

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